

DESIGN OF MULTI-PIN JOINTS IN COMPOSITE LAMINATED PLATE

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ABSTRACT

The paper presented here is the strength design of fiber reinforced composite laminates containing single or multiple pin loaded holes. The holes are arranged either in series or parallel. The continuity laws between pins and plate were used to calculate the distribution of pin loading, and finite element method to analyze the distribution of stress in the vicinity of holes. Finally the failure load is predicted by means of a failure criterion. Friendly a user computer code is developed to efficiently generate the appropriate mesh and boundary conditions for different geometry variables such as number of holes, sizes of holes and the plate, and holes positions. In order to testify the correctness of results, lots of experiments are also carried out to measure load corresponding to the carbon /epoxy MRL7401 laminates with different ply orientations and multiple pin joints. Comparisons between the experimental and the predicted results are found to be reasonable. Therefore, figures and tables of strengths versus different geometry variables provide a good reference in design.

1. INTRODUCTION

It's well known that multi-pin joints in composite laminated plate is important. Generally speaking, there are two methods to join parts: mechanical joint and adhesive bond. Although the performance of adhesive bond are superior to that of mechanical joint, the latter processes some excellent characteristics that cannot be replaced by the former. For example, it is easy to disassemble and has higher reliability etc.

In this study, composite material used was anisotropic and its properties strongly depend on the orientation and the strength provided by fiber. A material may cause stress concentration due to local fiber failure, such as made by drilling process. Such sharp stress fields are the main cause of damage. However, the mode and the size of damage is influenced by many factors, such as material quality, ply orientation, thickness, hole size,

and the distance between the hole and edge. To obtain an optimal design of these parameters and have a systematic study for joint theory and strength is necessary. In this study, the finite element method and Tsai failure criterion are used for theoretical prediction and a number of experimental cases are performed. Comparisons between the simulated and the experimental results are made and a reference manual of joint design was developed.

2. THEOREM

It is quite complicated to predict the failure strength of composite materials. In practice, structure often causes failure with mixed modes. Such among fiber breakage, matrix cracks, and delamination. Also the manufacturing process significantly affects the strength of structures. The strength of mechanical joints was predicted by using finite element analysis and the failure criterion with one order or two order terms. Simulated results were compared with the experimental results. If error values were caused by other factors, the simulations were modified accordingly.

Tsai-Hill failure criterion:

The criterion can be characterized by considering its plane condition.

$$\text{DIST} = \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X_C^*}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_C^*}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_C^*}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{X_C^*}\right)^2 \quad (1)$$

where X_C^* = the strength of longitudinal tension or compression
 Y_C^* = the strength of transverse tension or compression
 S_C^* = shear strength

If $\text{DIST} < 1$, the material will not fail. If $\text{DIST} \geq 1$, failure will occur. According to J.P. Wasiaczak and T.A. Cruse's study [1], this criterion cannot predict exact strength effectively. However, it does give a quick approximation.

In this study, two-dimensional finite element analysis was used to calculate the stresses and the strains of the composite laminated plate. Tsai-Hill failure criterion was used to predict the strength around the joint. The procedure of evaluation was at first to solve the strains of each ply from its complete thickness and then solve the stress of each ply, finally, obtain the strength ratio of each ply from the Tsai-Hill failure criterion. The strength of the plate could be evaluated by the ratio.

For the two-dimensional finite element, the relationship between unit width force and plane strain is

$$[N_i] = [A_{ij}] [\epsilon_i^0] \quad i=1,2,6 \quad (3)$$

or $[\epsilon_i^0] = [A_{ij}] [N_i]$

where $[N_i]$ =unit length force matrix

$[\epsilon_i^0]$ =plane strain matrix

$[A_{ij}]$ = extensional stiffness (4)

$[A_{ij}] = [A_{ji}] \quad i=1,2,6$

$j=1,2,6$

The principal strain, $\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y,$ and ϵ_{xy} , of each ply can be solved from plane strain $[\epsilon_i^0]$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = [T] \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1^0 \\ \epsilon_2^0 \\ \epsilon_6^0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$[T] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \theta & \sin^2 \theta & 2 \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ \sin^2 \theta & \cos^2 \theta & -2 \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ -\sin \theta \cos \theta & \sin \theta \cos \theta & \cos^2 \theta - \sin^2 \theta \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus, The principal stresses σ_x, σ_y and σ_{xy} , of each ply are

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = [\bar{Q}] \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where $[\bar{Q}]$ =components of modulus

Next, σ_x, σ_y and σ_{xy} , are substituted into Tasi-Hill failure criterion

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_x}{X}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_y}{Y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{xy}}{S}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_x \sigma_y}{X}\right) = e^2$$

where X: The strength in the fiber direction (0 degree)

Y: The strength in the direction perpendicular to the fiber (90 degree)

S: The shear strength

The larger the value of "e" is, the more likely failure will occur. If the value of "e" is greater than 1, $e > 1$, the plate will failure. Therefore, The maximum value of e was taken as design index. In a finite element simulation, the external load conditons could be taken arbitrarily.

The results of the stresses were proportion to the external loads(Typically the unit external load was taken). If the external load was P_0 and the maximum value of e, e_{max} , was obtained, the strength, P_{max} , of the mechanical joint could be expressed as

$$P_{max} = \frac{P_0}{e_{max}} \quad (7)$$

In this study, a computer code, "BOLTALL", is designed to efficiently analyze the strength of mechanical joints. Specially, it applies excellent stress analysis for complicated geometry of composite materials by auto-mesh generator. It also could efficiently generate boundary conditions for different geometry variables such as number of holes and size of holes and plates, and hole geometry. For example, $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminate was simulated and showed in Figure(1). The diameter of each individual hole is 5 mm, The width of the plate is 10 mm. The finite element mesh is shown in Figure(2). The finite element mesh can also be generated according to the varied width, referring to Ref(17). An another different geometry variable is shown in Figure(3).

FIG.(1) Geometry of three series joints

FIG.(2) Auto-mesh of three series joint

FIG.(3) Auto-mesh of different geometry variables

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After the composite laminated plates with mechanical joints were exerted by external load, there were several failure modes, which could occur such as bearing failure, net tension failure, shear out failure, sleeve failure, combination failure and pin failure. In this study, finite element simulation was used to analyze four types of composite laminated plates: $[0]_1$, $[\pm 45]_4$, $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2s}$, and $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2s}$, respectively and experimental data were made. Comparison between the simulated and the experimental results were presented (Tab.1-4). In addition, The geometry factor of those composite laminated plates would be

varied by the width and the distance between two series joints,gv. A number of cases are used to confirm the accuracy of the design approach .

3.1 The analysis of Specimen with single and multi joint

The types of the specimen are listed as the following tables.

The types of laminates

laminate lay-up	[0]16	[±45]4s	[0z/±45]2s	[0/90/±45]2s
type	a	b	c	d

The types of two series joint specimens

gv \ w	10	20	30	40
7.5	A11	A12	A13	A14
15	A21	A22	A23	A24
22.5	A31	A32	A33	A34

The types of two parallel joint specimen

w	15	30
type	B1	B2

The types of single joint specimen

w	7.5	10	15
type	C1	C2	C4

The specimens are carbon /epoxy MRL 7401 laminates. The properties are

- $E_x = 13480 \text{ kg/mm}^2$
- $E_y = 750 \text{ kg/mm}^2$
- $G_{xy} = 436.8 \text{ kg/mm}^2$
- $v = 0.3$
- $S_x = 196.7 \text{ kg/mm}^2$
- $S_y = 4.46 \text{ kg/mm}^2$
- $S_{xy} = 9.16 \text{ kg/mm}^2$

The theoretical and experimental results are shown in Table1-4 For [0]16 laminated, though the analytic results were conservative, the prediction of strength was approximate exact. When the distance between two joints was increased, the distribution of the pin forces was gradually transferred to the second joint. Therefore, the edge of the second joint would cause pin failure, and the strength was decreased. In finite element analysis of the case, the strength increases were not sensitive to increasing in the gv distance ; However, the

difference between the theoretical and experimental value was maximum when the ratio of W/D was at the minimum value. Such an design should be avoided. According to the results, The analytic results needed to be modified when the distance of gv was large. The modified factor proposed here is between 1.1 and 1.3. From the simulated results in the table, the maximum value of strength is shown to lie between $1 < W/2 < 2$ for parallel joint specimens.

For specimen of $[\pm 45]_{4s}$, the failure modes were complicated. This type of laminate always caused failure in large deformation. The non-linear deformation theorem was used to analyze the specimens. Therefore, the results of strength which were generated by linear-theorem were conservative . However, the tendency of strength in both analysis and experiment was the same in this case.

For specimens of $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2s}$, the results shown that this kind of laminate had the property quasi-isotropic. The simulated and the experimental values were almost identical. For each case , the strength reach maximum when the value of W/D was equal to two , $W/D=2$.

For the $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminate, tension failure was caused when the value of W/D was equal to two. Under these conditions the analysis value of strength were conservative . The other results were similar to that of $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2s}$.

In summary, although the simulated and the experimental values was not completely correct in some cases , the tendency of strength in all cases was the same .

Also, it is very useful to analyze the strength of mechanical joint by using this design approach. In design, if the property of laminate plate was isotropic and the ratios of specimen width to joint radio were not too small, the predicted values were be identical to the experimental value. The results were shown as Figure 4-7.

TABLE 1 $[0]_{16}$ The results of experiment(Tu), analysis(Tsf), and modification of analysis(Tsf)* for specimen $[0]_{16}$

Type	aA11	aA21	aA31	aA12	aA22	aA32	aA13	aA23	aA33	aA14
Tu kg/cm	8.96	12.5	18.1	5.85	7.66	9.20	3.89	4.65	6.40	2.89
Tsf	5.6	7.4	7.9	3.22	4.08	4.9	2.18	2.71	2.8	1.62
Tsf*	5.6	7.67	11.1	3.22	4.21	5.06	3.18	2.71	2.8	1.62

Type	aA24	aA34	ac1	ac 2	ac3	-aB1	-aB2
Tu	3.29	4.91	11.65	8.14	5.56	12.6	6.32
Tsf	2.1	2.9	4.7	4.6	3.6	5.4	3.7
Tsf*	2.1	3.3	11.5	8.1	5.5	12.1	6.21

TABLE 2 $[\pm 45]_{4s}$ The results of experiment(Tu), analysis(Tsf), and modification of analysis (Tsf)* for specimen $[\pm 45]_{4s}$

Type	bA14	bA24	bA34	bA13	bA23	bA33	bA12	bA22	bA32	bA11
Tu	7.89	9.06	8.78	10.3	10.6	11.4	13.12	13.12	13.31	8.14
Tsf	4.78	5.41	5.48	5.9	6.8	7.2	7.1	8.10	8.3	6.21
Tsf *	4.78	5.8	5.48	5.9	6.8	7.2	7.1	8.10	8.3	6.21

Type	bA21	bA31	bB1	bB 2	bC1	bC2	bC3
Tu	8.19	8.53	5.22	9.46	2.22	6.73	9.53
Tsf	6.85	6.92	6.06	7.23	5.07	6.79	7.24
Tsf *	6.85	6.92	6.06	7.23	2.53	6.79	7.24

TABLE 3 $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2s}$ The results of experiment(Tu), analysis(Tsf), and modification of analysis (Tsf)* for specimen $[0_2/\pm 45]_{2s}$

Type	CA14	CA24	CA34	CA13	CA23	CA33	CA12	CA22	CA32	CA11
Tu	5.79	6.51	6.08	8.17	9.43	11.9	11.9	13.6	15.9	20.8
Tsf	5.27	6.35	6.69	7.16	8.66	9.22	10.17	12.9	14.5	16.3
Tsf *	5.27	6.35	6.69	7.16	8.66	9.22	10.17	12.9	14.5	16.3

Type	CA21	CA31	cC1	cC 2	cC3	cB1	cB2
Tu	24.43	27.26	13.8	10.8	8.82	18.02	10.01
Tsf	26.0	26.15	16.3	14.01	9.88	16.43	9.37
Tsf *	26.0	26.15	16.8	14.01	9.88	16.43	9.37

TABLE 4 $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2s}$ The results of experiment(Tu), analysis(Tsf), and modification of analysis (Tsf)* for specimen $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2s}$

Type	dA14	dA24	dA34	dA13	dA23	dA33	dA12	dA22	dA32	dA11
Tu	6.3	6.72	7.37	9.35	8.63	10.12	13.44	13.98	15	24.8
Tsf	5.94	7.60	7.62	7.45	9.49	9.75	9.45	11.44	11.58	9.64
Tsf *	5.94	7.60	7.62	7.45	9.49	9.75	12.9	15.67	15.70	19.2

Type	dA21	dA31	dC1	dC 2	dC3	dB1	dB2
Tu	27.15	27.84	14.3	11.39	11.15	15.55	9.06
Tsf	11.15	11.27	8.25	11.13	10.17	8.46	10.16
Tsf *	22.3	22.57	12.37	11.13	10.17	12.68	10.16

FIG. 4 ---FEM + EXPER

FIG. 5 ---FEM + EXPER

FIG. 6. ---FEM EXPER

FIG. 7

3.2 THE SERIES SPECIMENS OF THREE AND FOUR JOINTS

The dimension and type of the specimen was shown in Figure 8 and Table 5

TABLE 5

FIG. 8

TYPE	thickness	tensile force
CE1-1	2.09	503
CE1-2	2.10	515
CE2	2.14	629

Comparison between the simulated and the experimental results was shown as follows:
 TABLE 6 The experimental and the analytic results of the three and four series joints

	CA12	CE1	CE2
experiment	11.9	12.73	15.73
analysis	10.17	10.7	14.7

Generally speaking, the analysis of parallel joints was not complicated. The strength obtained from analyzing the single joint was similar to that of the two parallel joints. In this section, each ply would be evaluated by varying the factors of W/D and gv/D.

For the $[0]_{16}$ laminate, The value of W/D at the maximum strength could be obtained from the strength-W/D curve. It was discovered that small widths such as W/D=2, were avoided in designs.

The good unidirectional strength of $[0]_{16}$ was not prone to cause tension failure; therefore, the strength was not decreased when the value of W/D was as low as 1.4. In Figure 9, the value of W/D was suggested to take between two and three. In Figure 10, the strength was increased as the distance of gv was increased under the condition that the value of W/D was two, W/D=2. In Figure 11 the strength difference between the parallel and the series joint was not large, the former was smaller than the latter when the value of w/D was increased.

For the $[\pm 45]$ laminate, the strength was maximum when the value of W/D was three. The large strength was caused between W/D=2 and W/D=3, shown in Figure12-14. In addition, the strength-gv/D curve was not shape, but quite smooth.

FIG. 9 Strength-W/D curve of $[0]_{16}$ laminate FIG.10 Strength-gv/D curve of $[0]_{16}$ laminate

FIG. 11 comparison the strength of single joint , double series joint and double parallel joint

FIG. 12 Strength-W/D curve of [45/-45] laminate

FIG. 13 Strength-gv/D curve of [45/-45] laminate

FIG. 14 comparison the strength of single joint double series joint and double parallel joint

The strength of the $[0_2/\pm 45]$ laminate was larger than any other one. The strength-W/D curve was sharp between $W/D=1.6$ and $W/D=3.0$, shown in Figure 15-17.

The $[0/90/\pm 45]$ laminate had failure because of tension and shear out mode. If the value of W/D was taken to be greater than two, $W/D > 2$ the analysis results were very good, as shown in Figure 18-20.

FIG. 15 Strength-gv/D curve of $[0_2/\pm 45]$ laminate

FIG. 16 Strength-W/D curve of $[0_2/\pm 45]$ laminate

FIG. 17 comparison the strength of single joint double series joint and double parallel joint

FIG. 18 Strength-gv/D curve of $[0/90/\pm 45]$ laminate

FIG. 19 Strength-W/D curve of $[0/90/\pm 45]$ laminate

FIG. 20 comparison the strength of single joint, double series joint and double parallel joint

4. CONCLUSION

Finite element analysis and the Tasi-Hill failure criterion were used in this study. The experimental method was designed not only to demonstrate the theoretical results, but also to supply a good design reference for multi-pin joints in composite laminated plate. There were five conclusions as following:

- (1) The strength reduction was effected more largely by the width than by the joint radius, and more by joint radius than by the distance between the joint and the edge.
- (2) For large width plate, the use of multiple parallel joint is recommended in order to increase the strength.
- (3) The simulated strength of multi-pin joint was always lower than its experimental data. This data might be a useful reference in the design process.
- (4) The predicted strength was in good correlation with those isotropic composite laminated plates.
- (5) The ratio of plate width to joint radius should not be too small; otherwise, the strength would be decreased due to the shear plane. In designs, the distance between the joint and edge was shown to be three. However, the strength were not apparently higher at the large distance.

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